

Deliverable 1.1

Competition Infrastructure Handbook (a)

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Deliverable author(s):	Sven Schneider, Deebul Nair, Gerhard Kraetzschmar BRSU
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List of acronyms

CFH	Central Factory Hub
EBM	Episode Benchmark
ERL	European Robotics League
FBM	Functionality Benchmark
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
RSBB	Referee, Scoring and Benchmarking Box
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TBM	Task Benchmark
UML	Unified Modelling Language

1 Introduction: Setting the Terminology

The work package WP1 in SciRoc investigates technical challenges and enhances the technical infrastructure across the different *European Robotics League (ERL)* tournaments and, hence, also the *SciRoc (Smart Cities Robotics) Challenge*. Here we can build especially on the results of the preceding, EU-funded projects RoCKIn, euRathlon and RockEU2. In particular we will identify best practices and lessons learned from those projects and show how they have been considered in designing and improving the ERL tournaments, as well as the SciRoc Challenge.

We follow the process of designing competitions that has been outlined in the RoCKIn deliverable D1.1¹ and is visualized in [Figure 1.1](#). To keep this Deliverable self-contained, we provide a short summary of this process. One of the driving forces behind a competition is the formulation of a *challenge*. In the SciRoc context those challenges build the foundation of the three individual leagues:

- ERL Professional Service Robots (*ERL Professional*): How can mobile manipulation robots support *low-volume, high-variety* manufacturing?
- ERL Consumer Service Robots (*ERL Consumer*): How can mobile manipulation robots support (elderly) citizens in their domestic environment?
- ERL Emergency Robots (*ERL Emergency*): How can multi-domain robotic systems support rescue teams in emergency situations?

Finally, the SciRoc Challenge integrates all three leagues in a common scenario of a Smart City. This particular challenge revolves around the question of how autonomous robots can support citizens in various *smart shopping* tasks.

While the challenges frame the overall benchmarks and competitions they are too complex to be solved within a reasonable time frame like a single EU-funded project and too generic to be solved by individual researchers. Thus, in a next step, interesting scenarios are derived from the challenge. A scenario consists of the *task* to be solved, the *environment* in which this task will be executed and the *robot* that will solve the task. Each of those three categories is defined in terms of their *features*, that is, a specification of the possible or allowed variability.

¹ http://rockinrobotchallenge.eu/RoCKIn_D1.1.pdf

Figure 1.1: Competition design process

From the perspective of a scientific experiment the features are free or fixed parameters. The definition of a scenario also gives rise to a list of (abstract) *functionalities* that a robot is required to have. Examples of such functionalities may include task planning, manipulation, grasping, visual object recognition, speech understanding or speech generation.

It should be noted that the scenario definition purely describes an application domain, but, by design, is not meant to provide insights into a robot's performance in solving a particular task in that domain. This latter aspect is addressed in the *benchmark (competition) definition* phase where the goal is to define *tests* that evaluate a robot's performance. The first step is the definition of *questions* or hypotheses that should be addressed by the benchmark. Only the right questions allow constraint of the overall design space of a scenario to a competition scenario where few, explicitly chosen features can be varied. The feature variation characterizes each benchmark test by a choice or instantiation of all relevant features. Three major aspects govern those choices:

- The *specification* aspect determines how the feature is described. For some features concrete properties and attributes can be asserted, for instance, in terms of values or enumerations ("imperative" specification). One example is the size of a room measured by width, length and height. In contrast, other features are better described via exemplifying representatives ("declarative" specification). An example is the specification of an object as a "coffee mug".
- The *temporal* aspect determines at which point in time the feature is instantiated. The choices vary from the scenario specification (e.g. the types of areas), over the testbed setup (e.g. the concrete size of areas), before the benchmark experiment execution (e.g. the location of manipulable objects) to during the benchmark experiment execution (e.g. outdoor light conditions).
- The *control* aspect determines the manner in which the parameters are specified or fixed. The choices vary from concrete values (e.g. runtime of an experiment) over ranges (e.g. allowed minimum and maximum size of areas) to unspecified conditions (e.g. outdoor weather).

Given different feature variations their impact on the robot's performance can be measured and compared via well-defined *metrics*. Similarly, benchmarks for the functionalities are defined. The steps to conduct the benchmark are described in the *benchmark procedures*. One artifact of particular interest that is compiled during this phase is the rulebook which communicates and clarifies the taken decisions and procedures to various stakeholders.

The next phase is the *benchmark experiment execution* where the tests are instantiated and robots solve the tasks in the real-world environment. The execution consists of the three

activities (i) scenario setup, (ii) experiment control; and (iii) data collection. In particular, the latter two activities can and should be supported by technical means that are described in this document. In the final phase, the resulting experimental data, also from multiple instantiations of benchmark experiments, is analyzed to provide answers to the questions underlying the benchmark definition.

The process above is a first step in guiding the design of robotic competitions. However, it still leaves open which actors participate in each phase's activities and what their role is. Hence, in this document we establish the link between those activities and the various competition stakeholders that we have identified in the SciRoc Deliverable D3.3 in particular for the *ERL Professional* league and a rough description of their role. For completeness we summarize and briefly explain the stakeholders here:

- As *beneficiaries* we consider them to be any stakeholders that benefit from the deployment of a robotic system. In a concrete context the beneficiary can be instantiated to a more specific entity. For instance, in *ERL Professional*, the beneficiary is an enterprise/for-profit organization, while it (usually) is a nonprofit organization like an emergency response team in *ERL Emergency*. In the *ERL Consumer* league and the *SciRoc Challenge*, the target group or beneficiary are individual citizens. Beneficiaries are the main source of challenges, but do not (necessarily) have a technical background in robotics and are usually interested in robust and reliable robotic solutions.
- Researchers work on innovative solutions to specific and focused robotics problems.
- Participating team
- Benchmarking expert
- Public audience
- Local organizer: the “hardware” guys, “booth builders”, not aware of and don't care about robots or benchmarking.
- Organizing committee: the “software development” guys, scheduling, communicating with teams, realize/implement/enforce the software/benchmarking specifications provided by the competition designer.
- Competition designer

Below we describe the general features that define each element of the competition (scenario) infrastructure and demonstrate it along with particular instantiations for the three ERL leagues as well as the SciRoc Challenge. For modelling the features, we rely on the visualization by feature diagrams and a more informal description via natural language. Additionally, we establish the relations between the stakeholders and their activities related to the competition infrastructure. Due to the rather abstract nature of those descriptions we employ the well-established Unified Modelling Language's (UML) use case diagrams.

2 Competition Scenario Infrastructure

Based on the different aspects of a competition, the infrastructure are:

- Tasks
- Environment
- Network embedded devices
- Benchmark execution control
- Data acquisition tools
- Robots

In the section below we will look in detail about each of these aspects.

2.1 Tasks: Past, Present, and Future

2.1.1 General Information on Tasks

A first step in each competition is the definition of the type of benchmarks to be executed. Existing robotic competitions like RoboCup², RoCKIn³ and DARPA robotics challenge⁴, frequently focus on benchmarks or tests that are attractive to the audience while still posing challenges to the participating teams. Since the execution of one benchmark run lasts rather long (e.g. up to ten minutes) they are seldom repeated more than once, hence (i) not providing much benchmark data to the benchmarking experts; and (ii) this may be frustrating for the teams if their robot fails exactly during that run. Additionally, such benchmarks require rather elaborate setups from the teams' side. Thus, already in RoCKIn we have defined two types of benchmarks that are continued in the ERL leagues:

1. Functionality Benchmarks (FBM) are very limited in scope so to (stress) test one individual functionality. By design, they are short (with durations around few seconds to around a minute) so that they can be repeated frequently. Consequently, FBMs are not too interesting to watch for the general audience. However, they are easier to implement for the teams when compared to elaborate tasks that require the integration of multiple functionalities. Additionally, FBMs provide more benchmarking data due to the repetitions.

² "RoboCup: The Robot World Cup Initiative." <https://www.aai.org/Papers/ICMAS/1996/ICMAS96-082.pdf>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

³ "RoCKIn and the European Robotics League: Building ... - Springer Link." 1 Nov. 2017, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-68792-6_15. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

⁴ "The DARPA Robotics Challenge Finals: Humanoid Robots To The" <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-319-74666-1>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

2. Task Benchmarks (TBM) are inspired by tasks in other robotic competitions and evaluate multiple, *integrated* functionalities in an application-oriented scenario. As such, they lie on the opposite side of the spectrum when compared to FBMs. They are wider in scope and repeated less frequently than FBMs, but usually more attractive to the general public by the practical relevance of the tasks. Due to the complex integration required from the teams the robots tend to fail more frequently in those elaborate tasks, which may counteract the TBMs attractiveness for the audience. Still those tests are designed with benchmarking and scientific evaluation in mind and various types of benchmarking data is recorded.

For the SciRoc Challenge an additional benchmark type has been defined as an intermediate between FBMs and TBMs, the Episode Benchmark (EBM). The EBMs test only (i) a limited set of integrated functionalities, for instance, wiping the floor as the integration of perception and manipulation functionalities; or (ii) variations in FBMs, such as extending a general navigation functionality to spatially constrained spaces like elevators. In terms of scope, complexity, entry level and repetitions those benchmarks are a middle ground between FBMs and TBMs. The name originates from the coherent embedding of multiple such benchmarks in a wider narrative like a smart city, as realized in the SciRoc Challenge. In addition, the limited scope increases the attractiveness for teams from different ERL leagues and further competitions, hence, enabling cross-league competitions.

[Figure 2.1](#) summarizes the different benchmark types as a feature model. It can be seen that the choice of the benchmark type is a real alternative, i.e. exactly one type of benchmark must be selected. It is the competition designers obligation to (i) define the available types; and (ii) choose and then realize the concrete tests according to those constraints. Here, the competition designer may be supported by the benchmarking expert.

[Figure 2.2](#) explains the use case diagram of defining episodes for a competition. It involved selection from the pool of tasks, frequently with the help of beneficiaries (maybe represented by advisory board) or participating teams. Activities in the use case diagrams frequently also involve repeated execution or iterations, for instance, to refine or improve previously created artifacts. Based on the user stories and application requirements a challenge is defined.

[Figure 2.3](#) explains the use case diagram for benchmark selection. The actors here are the competition designer and the different researchers. Based on the user stories and application requirements of the beneficiaries, they identify different tasks and functionality which can be converted as proper benchmarks. These different functionalities can be added to complete a task or similarly different tasks can be combined to complete an episode.

Figure 2.3: Use case diagram of the task and functionality benchmark definition

Different task and functionality benchmarks currently selected for the European Robotics League and SciRoc are mentioned below.

2.1.2 ERL Professional Robots

- TBM:
 - Pick from a box
 - Fill a Box with Parts for Manual Assembly
- FBM:
 - Object Perception Functionality
 - Manipulation Pick Functionality
 - Manipulation Place Functionality

2.1.3 ERL Consumer Robots

- TBM:

- Getting to know my home
- Welcoming visitors
- Catering for Granny Annie's Comfort
- Visit my home
- FBM:
 - Object Perception Functionality
 - Navigation Functionality
 - Speech Understanding Functionality
 - People Perception Functionality
 - Person Following Functionality
 - Object Grasping and Manipulation Functionality

2.1.4 ERL Emergency Robots

- TBM:
 - Yacht accident in the harbour (land+sea)
 - Emergency in a building (land+air)
- FBM:
 - 2D mapping functionality (land)
 - Mapping functionality (air)
 - Object recognition functionality (land)
 - Object recognition functionality (sea)
 - Object recognition functionality (air)
 - Vertical wall mapping functionality (sea)

2.1.5 SciRoc Challenge

- EBM:
 - Deliver coffee shop orders
 - Take the elevator
 - Serve goodies
 - Open the door
 - Fast delivery of emergency pills

2.2 Environment

The section describes in more detail the different selection criteria in an environment for conducting the competition.

2.2.1 General Information on Environments

The environment is designed to consider the following conditions

- almost identical to the real scenario,
 - it's a *model* of the real professional/domestic/emergency environment, hence it focuses on those elements that are relevant to the scenario (in particular the task and the robot)
- audience shall have clear visibility of the scenario
- replication:
 - made from easily available materials, such that all teams and the organizer can easily reproduce it
 - standardization
 - financial cost
- Features:
 - Spatial areas and/or rooms
 - Type (indoor room, outdoor ground/air/(under)water)
 - Amount
 - Topology, connectivity
 - Elevation (flatness, storeys, stairs, ramps)
 - Size
 - Boundaries (e.g. perceivable boundaries like walls, fuzzy boundaries between openly-connected living room and kitchen, “open area” with defined dimensions for UAVs)
 - Physical attributes:
 - general: temperature, light intensity, light temperature, electro-magnetic interference, acoustic noise level
 - water: salinity, visibility, current
 - ground/air: air pressure, humidity
 - weather conditions (rain, wind, dust)
 - Objects:
 - Obstacles (walls, furniture, machinery, debris, stones, holes, vegetation)

- Task role: perception-relevant, navigation-relevant, manipulation-relevant
- Amount & uniqueness
- Appearance: shape, size, material
- Movability & mobility
- (Manipulation) handle

2.4 Benchmark Execution Control

2.4.1 General Information on Benchmark Execution Control

The benchmark execution control is the central control unit to orchestrate the benchmark execution. It can be centralized software or a human operator. The referee and teams, along with the robots operate the benchmark only in accordance to the benchmark execution control. It should preferably be linked with data acquisition, and as a result the data acquisition starts when the benchmarking execution control starts the benchmark.

It serves as referee boxes during the task benchmarks to inform the robots about the different tasks to be done. It can also be used to record online data acquisition from the robot, such that the robot can provide information on its current actions back to the referee box.

The Benchmark execution control also records the timing of the benchmarks. Based on timings, data acquisition and the achievements made by the robot, the referee box can assign scores to corresponding benchmarks. When all the above activities can be automated the results calculation can be automated to make the process error-free and faster.

Figure 2.5: Visualization tool in ERL Professional

2.5 Data Acquisition Tools

2.5.1 General Information on Data Acquisition Tools

Data acquisition tools are generally provided by the competition organizer, for instance, by tracking the trajectory of a physical point of the robot, or by verifying if a given effect has been obtained by the robot. Another type of external benchmarking data refers to events that are part of a benchmark, such as what specific object has been presented to the robot during an object recognition benchmark. After deciding the benchmark, the organisers will select the parameters upon which the comparison between robots will be made. These parameters will then be recorded during the competition. The tool is mostly linked to the benchmark execution control. Thus the start and end of the data acquisition is controlled along with the benchmarks. The data can be made using external sensors and internal data of the robots can also be recorded.

Figure 2.7: OptiTrack used for data acquisition tool. Image Courtesy RockIn⁵

2.5.1.1 Data supplied by teams

For data acquisition not all data can be inferred from observing the robot from the outside. Frequently the participating teams themselves have no idea what is happening in the robot. This data is later used to match outside observation (see data acquisition tools) with robot's internal estimations/state. The data are collected online i.e. they are streamed by the robot to the testbed, or offline, i.e. recorded and later transferred to it. Examples of internal benchmarking data are the estimate of the robot's own pose as provided by the robot's own self-localization system, or the identification by the robot of a specific object instance among a set of candidates.

The data collected is used for the following analysis:

- "post-mortem debugging" and analysis for teams
- comparison between different teams and their approaches
- automatic evaluation and scoring
- monitor and trigger task execution progress

The data acquisition comes at a cost. The major problems which can be foreseen are:

- participating teams perceive it as overhead to provide the data
- standardization of interfaces/data formats can be difficult

2.5.1.2 Data from networked embedded devices

Networked embedded devices are frequently complex systems by themselves, composed of sensors, actuators and processing devices. Hence, they have access to a plenitude of

⁵ "RoCKIn." <http://rockinrobotchallenge.eu/>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

low-level to high-level data that is specific to their domain. For example, in an industrial setting, a computer numerical control (CNC) lathe or mill measures low-level actuator positions and velocities with extremely high precision and accuracy whilst also having access to the high-level program that it currently executes.

However, some problems associated with such domain-specific machines are:

- The manufacturers may choose not to expose all relevant data.
- Only a limited subset of the available data is useful for a robot. In the CNC use case, the actuator positions or velocities may not help an autonomous robot if it only needs to deliver material to that machine.
- They are expensive to acquire and operate, especially considering that they are only meant to be used as a mock-up.

2.5.1.3 Data from data acquisition tools

Here we mention the different modalities that can be recorded and their different categories by the data acquisition tools.

The different means of acquisition/modalities are:

- sensors
 - vision
 - motion tracking for localization
 - event/change detection
 - force/pressure sensors (e.g. to measure physical interactions)
 - microphone (for noise level)
 - thermometer
 - barometer
 - hygrometer
 - light meter
- state logging (from robot's interaction with benchmark execution control system or networked embedded devices)
- human/referee input
- autonomous robot report (see also 2.5.1.1)

2.6 Robots

Robots are the central point of attraction of the competitions. They are also the main use case for all the benchmarking that our league is performing. Robots are usually provided by the participating teams. There are some competitions where the organizer or a sponsoring company provides the robot. The general description of the robots for a scenario should consist of the following features.

Robot Type/Class

The competition should define the types of robots which can be utilised to compete in the competitions. The different categories can be based on different capabilities. For example some types of robots are bipedal, quadrupedal, mobile, static, manipulating etc. A more generic type can be based on maximum size allowed in the competition. For a benchmarking competition sponsored by a company, the robot or arena is fixed by the sponsor company. The definition of the type gives the competitors an idea about what is being tested in the competition.

Mobility Subsystems

What different kinds of mobility is allowed in the competitions? Different mobility subsystems available for robots are static, wheeled, tracked, legs(1, 2, 3, n), brachiation, aircraft (quadcopter, airship), underwater.

Manipulation Subsystems

Does the robots need to have manipulation capabilities? The different manipulation systems include robot arm, a dual arm subsystem, a forklift, a kicker, a pusher etc.

Grasping Subsystems

What kind of grasping subsystems are required? The different grasping sub systems are pinch gripper, parallel gripper, three-finger arm, five-finger arm, anthropomorphic hand or a pneumatic vacuum cup.

Sensor Subsystems

What different kinds of sensing capabilities does the robots have? What different sensing capabilities can the organizers provide? Sensors are the most important interface through which robots perceive the world and act upon it. Every year new efficient sensor modules are being developed. Based on the competition scenario the organizers can define the maximum sensing capabilities of the robots. For example, with humanoid robots, in order to be limited to human-like performances they constrain their sensor usage.

Communication Subsystems

How does the robot communicate to the base, referee box and amongst each other? Is it wired or wireless? What protocols are used? Are there any custom user defined protocols to

be implemented? Does the robot need to communicate with humans? Robots don't work in isolation, they work alongside humans or with other robots. In such a situation the modes of communication amongst each other has to be defined for the competition. Using the wireless mode of communication needs a plan for monitoring the wireless medium during the competition to identify if the allocated bandwidth is available for teams.

Power Supply

What different power supplies can the robots use? If the robots are static then they can have a constant power supply whilst mobile robots needs to be battery powered. What different kinds of batteries are allowed during competition? What is the maximum capacity of each battery?

Computational Subsystems

Computation sub systems are the brain of robotic systems. Which different computation subsystems are allowed in the robot? Does it need to be on the robot or can it be online? Are special computing devices like GPU, TPU allowed in the robot?

Features	ERL Consumer	ERL Professional	ERL Emergency
Type/Class	Autonomous, Human machine collaboration, Complaint, Indoor	Autonomous, Human machine collaboration, Indoor	Autonomous, Semi Autonomous, Remote Controlled, Outdoor and Indoor
Mobility	Static, wheeled, bipedal	Wheeled	Wheeled, underwater, quadcopter
Manipulation	No, Single and double arms	Single arm and double arms.	No and single arm
Grasping	Pinch gripper, parallel gripper, three-finger arm, five-finger arm, anthropomorphic hand	Pinch gripper, parallel gripper, three-finger arm, five-finger arm, anthropomorphic hand	Pinch gripper, parallel gripper, three-finger arm, five-finger arm, anthropomorphic hand
Sensor subsystems	Laser Scanner, Image sensor, RGBD sensor,	Laser Scanner, Image sensor, RGBD sensor,	SONAR, Laser Scanner, Image sensor,

	Voice sensor, speaker, touch sensor, LIDAR	Voice sensor, speaker, touch sensor, LIDAR	RGBD sensor, Voice sensor, speaker, touch sensor, LIDAR
Communication Subsystems	LAN, WiFi, LoWi,	LAN, WiFi	LAN, WiFi
Power Supply	Lithium ion power supply, Lead acid battery.	Lithium ion power supply, Lead acid battery	Lithium ion power supply, Lead acid battery
Computational Subsystems	Embedded systems, CPU. GPU, TPU	Embedded systems, CPU. GPU, TPU	Embedded systems, CPU. GPU, TPU

3 Competition Infrastructure

The competition infrastructure section will explain the different elements required for conducting a competition. The different infrastructure required for the organization of a competition are:

- Competition website
- Arena

3.1 Competition website

The competition website is an important piece of infrastructure for the competition. It's the main and the most important communication device with all the different stakeholders of the competition. Once the decision of running a competition is taken the competition website should be designed and made available with all the information.

The major categories in the website for a competition are:

1. Competition date
2. Competition schedule
3. Benchmarks planned

4. Registration details
5. Venue information
6. Benchmark results (current + previous)
7. Contact details of organizer

Responsibility: The competition organizer is responsible for maintaining the website. They must coordinate with the local facilitator and the teams to get the required information for the website.

3.2 Arena

The arena comprises of different spatial areas and the artifacts within them. These areas has to be marked appropriately and access to them needs to be well defined.

Figure 3.2 : Arena layout proposed for SciRoc 2019. Photo Courtesy: SciRoc⁶

⁶ "SciRoc." <https://sciroc.eu/>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

3.2.1 Spatial Areas of the Arena

The different spatial areas in the arena are:

1. Testbed

The Testbed is the central action place of the competition. While designing the location of the testbed it should be ensured that the testbed is centrally located, well lit and has maximum viewable area for an audience and the press.

The design of the testbed is provided by the competition organizer. The materials required for building the testbed can be decided between the competition organizer and the local facilitators.

2. Team working area

The team working area is the place where all the teams will be spending time for the whole period of the competition. The local facilitators should provide the basic amenities in the team working area; namely tables, chairs, electricity supply, LAN internet connection and storage place. The team working place should be near to the testbed but can be away from the audience. Teams should have easy access to the testbed from the working area. The team working area should not be accessible to the public. Security should be available for the team working area.

3. Organization area

The organization area will also have all the basic amenities like the team working area. In addition to those, the local facilitators should provide equipment required for visualization, namely display screens, microphones, speakers, notice boards, etc. The organization area is always adjacent to the arena. It would be ideal if the organization area is secluded from all the other areas.

4. Audience area

The audience should always have a good view of the testbed and the visualization materials. Safety measures should be taken to isolate the audience from the testbed. Special seating arrangements can be made for managing a large crowd. Clear instructions should be available for helping the audience to understand the competition.

Figure 3.3: Audience area in Robocup Leipzig, 2016. Photo courtesy: ERL⁷

5. Press area

Special areas should be marked for the Press so that they can cover the competition without issues arising from a large audience. The press area should be elevated to give a better view of the competition.

3.3 Competition Infrastructure Building

Building the infrastructure for the competition is spread over a long period of time and requires different inputs from different actors. Figure 3.1 shows the use case diagram involving the different infrastructure of the competition. The different actors involved with the infrastructure are:

- Teams
- Local facilitator
- Competition Organizer

In the beginning the local facilitator and the competition organizer come to a consensus that they need to do a competition on particular dates. Based on this information the competition organizer then creates the competition website and sends a notification to the teams about the planned competition. The teams based on information on the website, start the

⁷ "European Robotics League - euRobotics." https://www.eu-robotics.net/robotics_league/. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

registration process. Based on the participating teams the competition organizer will make a spatial plan for the competition. This includes spatial allocation for the teams, organizers, audience and the press.

Figure 3.4: Competition Infrastructure use case diagram

From this design the local facilitator plans all the required infrastructure and how to acquire them for the competition days. Also based on the registered teams and planned benchmarks, the competition organizer make a schedule for the competition. The competition organizer also has to provide the design of the testbed if its being set up by the local facilitators. If the testbed is being transported then the details needs to be sorted out between both of them.

The day before the competition the local facilitator along with the competition organizer sets up the arena and the testbed. The local facilitators provide the basic amenities for the teams, namely chairs, tables, internet connection etc. The competition organizer, in addition to the basic amenities, also provides the benchmarking equipment and visualization materials.

Since the performance evaluation of the robots is done using the wireless network, the success of the event relies on the network’s reliability and availability. As it is a shared

resource and during competition there is heavy usage, it's always a good idea to regulate the usage of the wireless medium. The competition organizer decides on the bandwidth allocation for teams and organizers. Everyone from the teams to the audience has to adhere to these rules. There should be constant wireless bandwidth monitoring to assure that the requested bandwidth by teams and organizer is always available.

3.4 Benchmark Execution Use Case

Figure 3.5 explains the use case diagram for benchmark execution. The actors involved during benchmark execution are the Competition organizer, teams, press and general audience.

Figure 3.5: Benchmark execution use case diagram

The Competition organizer prepares the schedule and the teams follow them to compete. The competition organizer also operates the referee box, benchmarking devices and gives scores to teams. He also makes the results available to the teams and the audience.

4 Safety Issues

Organizing competitions also involves looking into different safety issues. Safety issues are eliminated by mentioning the different potential threats during the competition. The different potential hazards and threats are:

- location/venue (e.g., see threats defined in “A 017 Gefährdungsbeurteilung⁸):
 - workplace
 - ergonomics
 - mechanical threats
 - electrical threats
 - substances
 - fire/explosion
 - special physical effects (e.g. sound, radiation, heat/coldness)
 - mental strain
- robots (mobile base, manipulator, drone, underwater robot)

The different measures to improve/guarantee safety are:

- Following safety standards:
 - ISO 31000⁹ (risk management process)
 - ISO 13849¹⁰ (safety of machinery control system)
 - IEC 62061¹¹ (safety of machinery)
 - A 107 (threat catalog)
- GSN
- technical means and/or regulations
 - emergency stop
 - human safety pilot for remote control
 - see D4.1 (5.1.5), also for possible problems
 - spatial separation of humans and robots
 - nets for drones

⁸ "Gefährdungsbeurteilung Gefährdungskatalog - BG RCI." https://www.bgrci.de/fileadmin/BGRCI/Downloads/DL_Praevention/VISION_ZERO_NULL_IST_DAS_ZIEL/A017_Gesamtdokument.pdf. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

⁹ "ISO 31000 Risk management - ISO." <https://www.iso.org/iso-31000-risk-management.html>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

¹⁰ "ISO 13849-1:2015 - Safety of machinery -- Safety-related parts of ... - ISO." <https://www.iso.org/standard/69883.html>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

¹¹ "EN IEC 62061 - Assess risks with the Safety Integrity Level - Pilz US." <https://www.pilz.com/en-US/knowhow/law-standards-norms/functional-safety/en-iec-62061>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

- fences
 - limitations (size, mass, actuation, ...)
 - safety inspections
 - safety certification
 - access control/restriction to areas (for robots and humans)

5 Security Issues

Competition organizers also need to look into the potential security issues when organizing competitions. Security can be both digital and physical and care should be taken of both. Computer security (confidentiality, integrity, availability) is required for all the computing devices such as benchmarking execution control and data acquisition tools all of which need to be secured from potential threats.

BSI IT-Grundschutz provides basic blocks and threat identification for security issues mainly:

- building blocks:
 - organisational and managerial aspects
 - security of the (hardware) infrastructure
 - security of IT systems
 - security in networks
 - security in applications
- threats:
 - force majeure
 - organizational deficits
 - human error
 - technical failure
 - deliberate act

Finally the measures to improve/guarantee security defenses are provided by:

- ISO 31000¹², risk management process
- IT Baseline Protection Catalogs (BSI IT-Grundschutz¹³)

These measures must be followed to avoid any security issues during the competition.

¹² "ISO 31000 Risk management - ISO." <https://www.iso.org/iso-31000-risk-management.html>. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

¹³ "IT-Grundschutz-Standards - BSI." https://www.bsi.bund.de/EN/Publications/BSIStandards/BSIStandards_node.html. Accessed 3 Sep. 2019.

6 Improving Audience Communication

An important element of the competition is education of the general public about robotics. Competition venues can be a good place to clarify the doubts amongst the general public about the capabilities of robots. Such communication needs to be planned appropriately based on the audience profile.

6.1 What the audience needs and wants to know

Before designing communication materials we have to understand the requirements of an audience. Below is some of the information an audience would need to understand about the competition:

- What is the competition about?
- What task is the robot supposed to be doing?
- What is the robot doing now?
- What performance criteria (speed, precision, ...) is used to decide the winner?
- What information does the robot have?
- Which teams are participating?
- What is the current overall status of the competition?
- When is the next competition?

The organizer has to prepare a communication strategy to answer these questions from the audience. There are 2 main ways of answering these questions; by human commentator and by visual display.

6.2 Human Commentators

Human commentators can explain the audience on the different aspects of the competitions during the run.

General guideline for the commentator can be:

- Describe the competition
- Describe the team
- Describe the robot
- Describe the task
- Describe the current action of the robot
- Final score of the run

Equipment needed:

- Microphone
- Speaker

6.3 Visual Displays

Visual displays are another effective way of passing information to the audience. The main advantage being that they are always available and can be read by the audience anytime.

The different means of visual displays are:

- Blackboard/Notice boards
- LCD/LED Screen

6.3.1 Blackboard/Notice boards:

To display the current status of the competition; which teams are participating and what are their corresponding scores.

	b-it-bots	LInDots	RoboHUB	robotTO	SMARTLAB
1st Round	18,75	650	188,75	450	
2nd Round	18,75	650	188,75	450	
3rd Round	850	/	0		
4th Round	25	150	25	/	250
5th Round	0	188,25	18,75	200	400
6th Round	3312,5			1100	
7th Round	18,75			18,75	

Contents which can be put on a notice board are:

1. Participating team names
2. Score of each round
3. Schedule of the competition
4. Time of the next competition

Figure 6.1: Notice board in German open 2019. Image Courtesy: b-it-bots

6.3.2 LCD/LED Displays:

They can be used to visualize different contents.

Below is a list of contents which can be visualized:

- Brief description of the league
- Brief description of the participating teams
- Description of the current task
- Status of the referee box
- Status from the robot

Figure 6.2: Robot displaying internal state in big screen. Image Courtesy: ERL Robotics league